

4.-5.10.2018 CAA Joint Chapter Meeting in Bochum, DE

The Joint-Chapter Meeting between the CAA Netherlands / Flanders and the CAA Germany will take place from 4th to 5th of October

in the House of Archaeologies in association with the German Mining Museum, Bochum Germany (Haus der Archäologien, Deutsches Bergbau-Museum, Bochum)

This year's JCM will be focused on discussing the "value of data in archaeology". This includes, but is not restricted to topics such as:

Big Data in Archaeology: the benefit and challenges of data mining in archaeology
Documentation in the Field: storing and analysis of data on mobile devices; interoperability of data
GIS Data for Landscape Analysis and Modeling
Reconstruction of the Past: analysing data for automated reconstruction and modeling
Data Relevant for Modeling and Testing Human Behaviour
Interpretation of Social Network Analysis in Archaeology

Programme

Thursday, 4th of October

09:30 Welcome

10:00 Nicolas Schimerl: Photogrammetric 3D documentation of underground sites

10:35 Georgios Karadimos: Digitising a Dutch Warship from the 18th century: Challenges and Perspectives

11:10 Felix Klein: The early Bronze Age gold mine of Sakdrissi: A 3D GIS evaluation of the archaeological findings

11:45 Lunch Break

13:00 Karin Göbel: Chamber grave "Poprad-Matejovce" – experience of 10 years GIS

13:35 Marina Gavryushkina: Pushing Possibilities: 3D GIS Spatial Analysis of Chlorakas-Palloures, Cyprus

14:10 Wilhelm Hannemann: Automatic object detection and segmentation in structure-from-motion mappings of historic mining sites

14:45 Coffee Break

15:30 M. Fabian Meyer: Automated detection of cultural heritage in digital terrain models of Westphalia

16:05 Benedikt Grammer: Archaeological remote-sensing and the organisation of spatial archaeological data – a perspective from eastern Austria

17:15 Benjamin Gehmlich: Large-scale image retrieval using a vocabulary tree

19:00 Dinner

Friday, 5th of October

10:00 Alex Brandsen: Using Text Mining to Unlock the Hidden Knowledge in Dutch Archaeological Reports

10:05 Gerald Hiebel: Big Data for Prehistoric Mining Archaeology

10:40 Benjamin Ducke: An Open Infrastructure for Archaeological Data from Field to Archives: idai.world

11:15 Lunch Break

12:30 Till F. Sonnemann: Teaching Digital Archaeology at Dutch, Flemish and German Universities

13:05 Barbora Weisssova: FAIMS in the Field: Regional Monitoring of Cultural Heritage in Bulgaria

13:40 Adela Sobotkova: FAIMS Mobile: Generalized Field Research Platform for and by Archaeologists
14:15 Coffee Break
15:00 Chiara Girotto: The interpretative value of spatial statistics – Are we narrating the past?
15:35 Eleftheria Paliou: Assessing the value of flow-balanced spatial interaction models for the study of long term settlement evolution: the case study of the Pontine region (Central Italy) from the Archaic to mid Imperial period (c. 600 B.C. – A.D. 250)
16:10 Frederic Schaff: Artificial Anasazi with Explicit Knowledge Representation and Population Model
16:45 Goodbye

Registration

Please register for the conference by sending an email to CAA2018Bochum@gmail.com, providing your full name and affiliation, as well as if you are a student or regular attendant (note that we also offer reduced rate for pensioners). Please try to send us your registration by the 16th of September.

Registration fee will be

20€ for regular attendants

15€ for students / reduced rate (this includes student presenters)

To be paid directly at the conference – apologies for any inconvenience.

The registration fee includes coffee, tea and drinks, but no lunch or dinner (see below).

Venue & Stay

The meeting will take place in the
“Haus der Archäologien” of the Deutsches Bergbaumuseum Bochum
(“house of archaeologies” of the German Mining-Museum, Bochum)

Please find a description of how to reach the place here
(https://www.bergbaumuseum.de/images/ueber-uns/lageplan_hda.pdf)

There are various hotels in easy reach of the venue, but please note that the Acora-Hotel in Bochum (<http://acora-bochum.de/>) offers a reduced fare for conference participants, if you mention the code “CAA Bochum” – note, however, that they only have a limited number of rooms available, so first come first serve ;)
Eating opportunities

There are various options for lunch and dinner in close proximity to the House of Archaeology and, of course, in Bochum in general.

Social Dinner

We have reserved seats at the Brauhaus Rietkötter (<https://www.brauhaus-rietkoetter.de/>) for the 4th of October, for those who want to join – self-paying, we are sorry to say. The Brauhaus offers us a choice of 4 dishes, including one vegetarian option. We would like to kindly ask you to indicate in your registration whether you would want to join the dinner, so that the restaurant can plan ahead accordingly. For details on the menu, please send us an email.

<http://ag-caa.de/caa-jcm-2018/>